

Bioconversion of polystyrene and food waste streams into biochar: An upgraded enzymatic activation system

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INTRODUCTION

Pyrolysis is a suitable strategy for managing two residues of global concern: plastics and food waste.¹ The addition of plastics to the pyrolysis of biomass (co-pyrolysis) seems to improve the sorptive properties of **biochar** (carbonaceous pyrolysis product).² However, one of the technical limitations of this type of co-pyrolysis is the different densities between materials, which limits the proportion of plastic in the mixture or forces a plastic pre-treatment to increase its density.³ To solve this technical limitation, the capability of some **insect larva** species to chew plastics emerges as a low-cost alternative method.⁴ Taking advantage of mealworm (*Tenebrio molitor*) voracity, we propose to use the **frass** (manure) from larvae fed with polystyrene (PS) and spend bread diets to produce biochar with upgraded features for enzymatic functionalization.

QUESTIONS

- Q₁ Can we obtain plastic-rich feedstocks for making biochar?
- Q₂ Did plastic addition to pyrolysis increase the adsorption of enzymes in biochar?
- Q₃ What about the thermal and operational stability of enzymatically activated biochar?

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

1) Frass production

2) Biochar production

PS (%)	Temp (°C)	Time (min)
0	300	90
10	300	90
0	600	90
10	600	90

RESULTS

1. Biochar produced at 600°C had a higher adsorption capacity for esterase and laccase enzymes than 300°C-biochar (data are mean±SEM, n=4).
2. Biochar from PS-containing frass retained a higher enzymatic activity on its surface, except for laccase incubated with 300°C-biochar.

KEY POINTS

- Q₁ **Yes!** We obtained a well homogenized and high PS-contained frass from mealworm larvae fed on plastic-spend bread diets.
- Q₂ **Yes!** Biochar derived from PS-containing frass displayed upgraded adsorption capacity for enzymatic activation with respect to biochar from control frass (spent bread diet).
- Q₃ Enzymes were active after biochar drying (30°C) and multiple biochar rinses, which opens biotechnological opportunities for the enzymatic remediation of contaminated water and soil.

Drying of biochar caused a loss of enzyme activity, but was less prominent for 10%PS-derived biochar dried at 30°C (bars are mean±SD, n=3).

The enzyme activity did not change after three cycles of enzyme assays (bars are mean±SD, n=3).

REFERENCES

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